

GIRLS' EDUCATION POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND FEMALE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS IN TWELVE YEARS BASIC EDUCATION IN RWANDA

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Abstract: This study entitled: “Girls' education policy implementation and female students' academic achievement in twelve years basic education in Rwanda”. Has conducted due to that the girls' policy implementation in twelve years basic education schools was critical in leading female students to the desired achievements where all students study at a day and return home in the evening. This study aimed at assessing the effects of girls' education policy implementation on female academic achievement in Gasabo District Rwanda. The study adopted descriptive and correlational research designs to get the required data. The population of the study was 220 teachers and head teachers of 10 selected schools in Gasabo District and the sample size was 142 computed using Slovin's formula. Primary data were collected using questionnaires and interviews on girl's achievements. The findings showed that the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education in Gasabo district was practiced at medium level because the results showed that there was still some gap to fill so that every female student at schools is integrated for academic achievement. The findings showed that the females' students practice many actions where some of them were appointed to assist their colleagues who have particular problems related to social life and education such as guidance and counseling, establishing saving groups and mobilizing their colleagues on the entrepreneurial education and how to fight against early pregnancies among teenagers. The researcher has recommended that stakeholders in education should provide enough and adequate sanitary equipment to the female learners to allow them learns in conducive environment.

Keywords: Girls Education Policy, Academic achievement, Twelve Years Basic Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, education is perceived as a recipe for change and development. Education enables an individual to develop analytical skills and sense of reasoning in addition to acquiring self-confidence and esteem among male and female. According to Anderson (2019), lack of education cripples the child in terms of income, health and access to opportunities. The Author proceeds by stating things might even become worse for a child without education in the coming years in terms of productivity and social welfare. This supports the fact that female education is critical to the child welfare and the mother.

Bruce (2016) further opines that girls' education contributes to reduced infant mortality and fertility rates among female. According to the Australia educational goals, both females and males have the same opportunities in secondary schools that lead to development of the country's knowledge and skills base regardless of sex. Literacy level experienced a boost

in Latin America between 2014 to 2018 from 72% to 83% nearing gender parity in literacy level. The school life expectancy of more than 10 years has been achieved in a number of developed countries and countries such as Chile, Cuba, Panama and Tunisia have also experienced the same (Elbakri, 2018).

According to Oxfam (2005) and Adetunde and Akesina (2008), politics also plays a role in girl's education as it can support or not support girls schooling. Some governments are still not willing to re align their policies to accommodate promotion of equity and equality in girls' education as envisaged in the third Millennium Development Goal. According to Glick (2008), gender neutral policies overlook costs and benefits of girls' education compared to boys while gender targeted policies does.

In the East African Context, Kenya recorded a lower gender parity index of 0.84 in 2010 (United Nations, 2010). This was above the middle and Western Africa which recorded GPI of 0.67 and 0.77 respectively putting East Africa in front in terms of moving towards equality in education. However, Glennerster *et al.* (2017) still stated that there is still low enrolment in secondary schools in Kenya for both gender. According to Republic of Kenya (2012) there has been an upward trajectory in terms of girls' enrolment since 2001 even though the enrolment of boys was still higher every year signifying a gender disparity hence inequality in education access (Republic of Kenya, 2012).

In Rwanda, girls' policy talks about gender disparity which is viewed to mean the unequal access to quality education by girls. In developing countries mainly, girls' education is not viewed as important and girls occupy little space in education as compared to boys in most societies. Additionally, socio cultural factors also act as a hindrance where boys are favored in most families when it comes to education.

Generally, the wider obstacle keeps on continuing to stop girls or boys going to school by giving them varied labour environments for family survival which leads to gender disparities in education. Many researches have conducted researcher and widely reports disparity in equal access to opportunities among girls and boys.

The scenario is not different form Rwandan experience where in 2006 primary six examinations, girls accounted for 37.91% which was below the boys who accounted for 62.09%. Moreover, in secondary school the disparity is even wider where girls accounted for 31.7% while boys accounted for 68.3% of those of who passed exams (2006 Tronc-commun results). The situation is more pronounced in tertiary level as reported by Ministry of Education statistics (2002) where girls only account for 26% (MINEDUC, 2002)

1.1 Problem Statement

In African countries like elsewhere in the world, education policies were introduced in education sector for the purpose of governing and giving clear line of all activities that take place in education (McMahon & Oketch, 2018). Among these policies include girls' policy which plays more than one role in both public and private secondary schools including day secondary schools and boarding schools where in public day secondary schools known as Twelve Years Basic Education.

The Rwandan government is committed to promoting access to quality education through 12YBE program and coming up with education policies that offer a conducive learning environment for better academic achievement for both girls and boys. However, reports have shown that in 12YBE, the performance of girls have relatively been low and varies from one school to another. Female education policies are meant to provide an equal better learning environment as their male counterparts hence promote academic achievement. Several researches have shown that proper implementation of education policies is paramount and of significant towards achievement of academic goals and particularly in Rwanda, for the success of 12 YBE to be realized, proper implementation of education policies is important. Girls face a lot of challenges as compared to the boys and therefore their improved academic performance needs a lot more focus and effort to be applied.

Despite the importance of education policy implementation in schools, little has been done in Rwanda to ascertain the extent of implementation of girls' education policies with focus on gender equity, gender equality and girls' education task force. With the challenge of low and varied academic achievement of girls in 12YBE, there is need to investigate the role of girls' education policies that are in place towards improving academic achievements. Therefore this study aims at determining the effect of girls' policy implementation (gender equity, gender equality and girl's education task force) on female students' academic achievement in 12YBE in Gasabo district, Rwanda.

1.2 General Objective

The general objective of this research was to assess the effect of girls' policy implementation on students' academic achievement in twelve years' basic education in Gasabo district, Rwanda.

1.3 Specific Objectives

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- i. To evaluate the extent of implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education in Gasabo district, Rwanda.
- ii. To examine the level of female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education in Gasabo district, Rwanda.
- iii. To determine the effect of girls' policy implementation on female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education in Gasabo district, Rwanda.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This research paper is significant as it will deal with current issue. Girls' policy implementation and female students' academic achievement has been pointed as major driver of quality education in 12YBE; hence; Girls' policy implementation and female students' academic achievement is attracting worldwide attention. This study will be of benefit to various education stakeholders including head teachers and teachers, parents, ministry of education among others.

Head teachers and discipline masters may benefit from this study where they will get more about girls' policy and how can affect female students' success and how to be implemented so that female students' academic achievement can be improved. Teachers will gain more about how to help female students to improve their academic performance through implementing girls' policy effectively.

Parents also will benefit from this study, where they will know how well girls' policy implementation contributes to female academic achievement which leads to positive effect on society. This will enable them to be part and parcel of implementation of girls' policies in order for their children to attain higher academic achievements. They will be much willing to support where possible the implementation of girls' policies which will ultimately benefit their children.

The Ministry of education (MINEDUC) it will benefit from this study where it will gain knowledge of how effective implementation of girls' policy contribute to better female students' academic achievement so that MINEDUC can make a follow up of how this policy is being implemented in 12YBE in Rwanda in order to improve female students' academic achievement.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Literature

This section discusses the concepts of girls' education policy implementation and female student academic achievement in 12YBE so as to clearly bring out the link between the two.

Girls' Education policy implementation

Girls' education policies are policies that are aimed at improving girls' access to education opportunities and able compete fairly with their male counterparts in employment and leadership positions (MINEDUC, 2008). Education policies exist in all countries both developed, developing and underdeveloped and they determine the success of the education sector in every country in terms of addressing societal needs. Better education policies contribute to economic development of the country by ensuring quality education, which results into provision of skilled manpower required in the job market in addition to promoting the societal moral virtues and behaviors. Education policies also ensure that the children are raised in an upright manner so as to take care of the future of the country since they are perceived as the future leaders. Education policies also play a greater role in achieving equity and equality in the education system. These policies are meant to be able to take care of the demands of all students to be able to achieve their education goals (Mutegi, *et al*, 2017).

Rwanda's Vision 2020 emphasized the need to promote gender equality and equity through education by revising education laws to provide a fair and favorable learning environment for both gender. Implementation of education policies is meant to create safe learning environment in school for the students to achieve education goals. There is need for schools to always get prepared to protect girls from unsafely conditions that may arise such as disasters, behavior changes or emergencies.

Rwanda education policies aims at promoting equality and equity in the education sector so that all the students both girls and boys are able to be successful. Among the education policies in place that promotes equality in the Rwanda education sector includes equal participation in sports, leadership and class works by students, equal assessment of students, equal provision of sanitation systems, provision of free tuition fees for all students in 12YBE, Education for all, provision of quality education among others (MINEDUC, 2003). On the other hand, policies that promote equity in the education sector focus on a specific disadvantaged group for example the girls may be disadvantaged even though there is equality. Girls need an extra attention hence the need to come up with particular policies that focus on girls alone.

Rwanda government through Education Ministry has come up with special policies that aim to uplift the girls to achieve their education goals. These policies include provision of sanitary pads, guidance and counseling on gender issues, girls sexual abuse protection, avoid stereotype on STEM subjects where girls are perceived not to perform well in science and technology subjects among others (MINEDUC, 2008). Additionally, there are policies that are implemented by the girls' education task force that aims to promote girls' education including integrated M&E for girls' education, sensitization programs on girls' education and creation of partnership and networks towards improving girl child education among others (MINEDUC, 2008).

Girls 'policy implementation and female students' academic achievement

According to Onoria (2007), approximately 36 million girls were out of school and there is poor service for girls in secondary schools. There has been a general rising trend in discrepancies in the number of boys and girls in tertiary and secondary schools. According to the Author, Matrons in schools play a significant role in schools and surprisingly some schools do not have one. This scenario begs the question on who takes care and monitors the provision of girls' special needs more so during their periods. According to FAWE (2016), limited guidance and counseling offered to girls reduces their performance. There is need for Matrons to create a cordial relationship with children (Twinomugisha, 2016).

Girls are also motivated by the presence of female teachers according to Evans (2006). When they see the female teachers, girls are motivated to work hard and be like them in future hence they act as their role models. Sanitation is a critical factor towards girls' academic performance. These include toilets, drainage systems and, sewage and waste management systems among others. Lack of better sanitation crates an unsafe learning environment negatively affecting academic achievement.

This implies that in those countries the participation rate f girls in education matters is higher and are less perceived as domestic workers contrary to developing countries. Gender inequality is reported to increase as you move higher education levels meaning that most girls do not advance their schooling due to several hindrances among them poor education policies which cause high dropout and repetition rates (Hyde, 2014, Hadija, 2012).

Government Policy and Female students' Academic Achievement

Girls' policy in Rwanda talks about gender disparities where this term refers to unequal access to quality education and educational achievement difference. In many developing countries; barriers towards girls' access and retention in both primary and secondary education where the secondary position of women in most male-controlled societies translates itself into viewing of education as not being as important for girls. In addition to this; cultural and Socio-economic factors play a part in some cases where families favor boys over girls for entrance in schools when quality education is not for free. Generally, the wider obstacle keeps on continuing to stop girls or boys going to school by giving them varied labor environments for family survival, which leads to gender disparities in education.

Many researches have been conducted and revealed that this issue contributes a lot denial or promotion of equal opportunities for boys and girls in education. Gender disparities in Rwanda also experienced repetition and performance,

which is taken as big issue as indicated by statistics of different years where the performance of 2006 indicated that 37.91% of girls passed the primary six examinations while the remaining 62.09% were boys. The gap widens in secondary school where only 31.7% of girls passed Tronc Commun exams while 68.3% of boys passed (2006 Tronc-commun results). As indicated by Ministry of Education statistics (2002); the situation becomes even worse at tertiary level where only 26% of undergraduates are girls.

2.2 Empirical Literature

By reading the thoughts presented by other researchers related to how girls' policy implementation related to female students' academic achievement, you can realize that girls' policy implementation is significantly related to female students' academic achievement. Hattie (2011) conducted a study in Routledge, London on the effectiveness of grouping in reducing inequalities in students' achievement in secondary and primary schools.

Jayaweera (2015) conducted study in Sri Lanka which was entitled the effect of socio-economic status on female students' academic achievement in secondary schools. The researcher used the descriptive research design and questionnaire as well as guided interview in data collection where questionnaires were given to students and guided interview given to head teachers for collecting both quantitative data and qualitative data. The researcher revealed that girls from families with high socio-economic status perform better academically as compared to those from poor families; the researcher concluded that socio-economic status has significant influence on female students' academic achievement.

In addition to this; the results have shown that girls policy implementation especially gender equity and gender equality seem to be the most cost effective way of increasing quality education in Africa. Mensah (2018) carried out research in Ghana aiming at determining the relationship between girls' policy and female education; the Information was collected from secondary teachers and head teachers as well as students by using questionnaires and guided interview.

There are inadequate sanitary facilities in a number of schools as reported by Babyegeya (2019). Most schools lack water, poor buildings, with old and inadequate classroom chairs among other physical facilities. According to FAWE (2016), facilities are very critical motivational needs to a learner and hence attract most students. Schools with better facilities stand a high chance to attract more learners than those with poor facilities. These facilities create an enabling environment for learning and more particularly girls are severely affected in an environment of lack of facilities than boys as they need extra care and facilities.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Behaviorism Theory

Behaviorism theory is the first concern in this theoretical framework that shows the aspects of human behavior. Some behaviorists who are the founders of this theory are B. F Skinner, Ivan Pavlov and Albert Bandura, in which they said that behavior is learnt and it can be replaced by new behavior. They also said that learning is the rewarded response in order to make learning more effective and to occur (Parkay & Hass, 2000).

In addition to this; female students' academic achievement in in Twelve Years Basic Education is influenced by girls' policy implementation where girls who attended schools where girls' policy implemented effectively are highly motivated to learning as behavior can be influenced by daily experience and hence; female students' academic achievement improved.

Social Learning Theory

Founder of this theory is Albert Bandura where he observed that human behavior can be changed through imitation of others behavior. The aspects of social learning theory include observation, retention, imitation and motivation. This theory shows that internal motivation can be accounted in the variation of behavior and in diverse of social influences especially girls' policy implementation produces diverse female students' academic achievement and this can promote female students' academic achievement.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

This is the diagram that provides a linkage of independent and dependent variables:

Source: Researcher (2022)

Figure 1

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted two research designs to address the problem namely descriptive survey design and correlation research design. Descriptive survey design aims to describe a phenomenon as it is and this was helpful in understanding the state of girls' academic achievements in schools as well as the extent of implementation of girls' education policies.

3.2 Sample Size Determination

This study is comprised by 220 people as the study population and sample size was determined by using Slovin's formula, (Yamane, 1967). Therefore the sample was 142 respondents as they are categorized in this table:

Table 1: Population and Proportioned Sample Size

Participants	Target population	Sample size
Head teachers	12	8
Teachers	208	134
Total	220	142

Source: Researcher (2022)

Both head teachers and teachers were selected in determination of sample size from respective schools that were involved in this study.

3.3 Sampling Technique

Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in this study where the population will be divided into groups called strata mainly teachers, while sampling the head teacher the researcher used purposive sampling due to their expertise and education policies implementation in their respective schools. The researcher also used proportionate method in order to get the representative of each stratum. The researcher used convenience sampling technique in choosing Gasabo District among three districts in Kigali City because it was nearer for the researcher to collect data quickly.

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher used the tool known as instrument of the research and those instruments can be developed (Oso & Onen, 2016). The instruments that were used in this study are interview guide and questionnaires. Both questionnaires and interview guide were used. The interview guide was given to 12YBE head teachers in order to get qualitative data that were the additional to the quantitative data gained from the given questionnaires to teachers.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents and return rate

The teachers and school leaders whose the researcher has sampled were comprised of 8 head teaches of twelve years basic education schools and 134 teacher of the same schools who made total of 142 respondents and all of them provided their views and opinions on the on Girls' education policy implementation and female students' academic achievements in Twelve Years Basic Education in Rwanda.

4.2 Presentation of the findings

This study entitled: "Girls' education policy implementation and female students' academic achievement in twelve years basic education in Rwanda, the researcher presented the study findings, analyzed them, interpreted them and discussed in line with the specific objectives.

The implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education

The researcher has evaluated the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education in Gasabo District, and the respondents' teachers and head teachers have provided their views regarding to their daily implementation of the Gils's policy to their academic achievements.

Table 2: Teachers' views on the implementation of girls' education policies

Statements	SD		D		N		A		SA		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
Girls participate in sports activities	12	9	11	8.2	21	15.6	46	34.3	44	32.8	20.2	11
Girls participate in leadership positions like class/ group rep	3	2.2	18	13.4	32	23.8	71	53	10	.7	19.5	16
There is adequate sanitary structures (toilet) for both boys and girls	9	6.7	18	13.4	7	5.2	64	47.7	36	26.8	19.9	12
There is girls room well equipped with bed, pads, soap, water, towel	4	2.9	23	17.1	7	5.2	51	38	49	36.5	22.9	14
Parents pay tuition fees for both girls and boys without any compromise	8	6	3	2.2	14	10.4	62	46.2	47	35	19.9	23
I practice protection of girls sexual abuse/ harassment	0	0	3	2.2	12	8.9	76	56.7	43	32	25.8	17

Source: Primary source (2022).

The researcher described the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education in Gasabo District, and the respondents were asked if girls participate in sports activities and 32.8% responded strongly agree, 34.3% responded agree, 9% responded strongly disagree, 8.2% responded disagree. When asked whether girls participate in leadership positions like class or group rep, .7% answered strongly agree, 53% answered agree, 2.2 answered strongly disagree while 13.4% answered disagree. The respondents were asked if there was an adequate sanitary structure (toilet) for both boys and girls, 26.8% answered strongly agree, 47.7% answered agree, 20.1% were in disagreement side. They were asked if there is girls room well equipped with bed, pads, soap, water, towel, 36.5% answered strongly agree, 38% answered agree, 2.9% answered strongly disagree while 17.1% answered disagree. They were asked whether parents pay

tuition fees for both girls and boys without any compromise, 35% responded strongly agree, 46.2% responded agree, only 8.2% were at disagreement side. The teachers were asked whether they practice protection of girls sexual abuse/harassment, 32% answered strongly agree, 56.7% responded agree, only 2.2% answered disagree. This shows that the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education in Gasabo district was practiced at medium level because the results showed that there was still some gap to fill so that every female student at schools be integrated for academic performances.

Interview with head teachers to evaluate the implementation of girls' education

During this study, the school head teachers were interviewed and provided their views on the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education and answered:

Head teachers were asked to describe the girls' achievements since girls' education policy implementation activities started from their schools and they responded: "Female students have got equal opportunities in schools and they perform like boys and sometime they even perform more than their brothers. They kept mentioning that when females are taken care of, they feel confident and participate into lessons effectively. According to the head teachers of the schools, when girls are given the opportunity to participate in the academic practices they bring about the achievements such as supporting in against gender based violence activities, against child abuse activities. The respondents mentioned that the females' students practice many actions and show positive discipline where some of them are appointed to assist their colleagues who have particular problems related to social life and education such as guidance and counseling, establishing saving groups and mobilizing their colleagues on the entrepreneurial education and how to fight against early pregnancies among teenagers.

Female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education

The researcher was interested in examining the level of female students' academic achievements in Twelve Years Basic Education and analyzed information from teachers and head teachers in the sampled 12YBE schools.

Table 3: Teachers' views on the level of female students' academic achievement

Statements	SD		D		N		A		SA		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%	Fre	%		
Girls' grades in exams/ assessments have improved overtime	20	15	31	23	2	1.4	52	38.8	29	21.6	23	13
Since girls' policy implementation, there is high girls promotion rate	24	18	21	15.6	9	6.7	46	34.3	34	25.3	32	12
Girls participation in learning has been increased	11	8.2	36	26.8	5	3.7	31	23.1	51	38	21	18
There is positive discipline among girls	6	4.4	33	24.6	27	20	48	35.8	20	15	24	16
Girls complete their homework on time	2	1.5	1	.7	5	3.7	94	70.1	32	23.8	19.1	34

Source: Primary source (2022).

The researcher described the level of female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education in Gasabo District, Rwanda, and the respondents were asked if girls' grades in exams/ assessments have improved overtime and 21.68% responded strongly agree, 38.8% responded agree, 23% responded strongly disagree, 15% responded disagree. When asked whether since girls' policy implementation, there is high girls promotion rate, 25.3% answered strongly agree, 34.3% answered agree, 15.6% answered strongly disagree while 18% answered disagree. The respondents were asked if girls participation in learning has been increased, 38% answered strongly agree, 23.1% answered agree, 8.2% answered strongly disagree, while 26.8 answered disagree. They were asked whether there was positive discipline among girls, 15% answered strongly agree, 35.8% answered agree, 4.4% answered strongly disagree, while 24.6 answered disagree. They were asked whether girls complete their homework on time, 23.8% answered strongly agree, 70.1% answered agree, 1.5% answered strongly disagree, while 0.7 answered disagree. This means that since the girls policy

started its implementation in Twelve Years Basic Education, the level of female students' academic achievement has increased at distinctive level where both girls and boys get equal opportunity to perform different academic activities and both succeed. The results revealed that the policy implementation had to keep getting implemented for sustainable academic achievements.

Interview analysis on the level of female students' academic achievement

During the study, the school head teachers were interviewed and provided their views on the level of female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education and answered:

"The level of female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education was on the distinctive level, female students are archiving more in the schools as boys, now no girls marginalized and left behind, all students are care of equally even though some females need particular special support such as having girls' room that is utilized by female during the studies. This girl's room, according to the head teachers, contains some basic materials which can be used by them females girls while in their menstruation periods.

The effect of girls' policy implementation on female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education

The researcher determined the effect of girls' policy implementation on female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education schools of Gasabo District:

Table 4: Teachers' views on the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education

Statements	SD		D		N		A		SA		Mean	Sd
	Fre	%										
Participation of girls in sports activities improves academic performance	4	3	16	12	29	21.6	57	42.5	28	20.8	19	17
Participation of girls in leadership increases academic achievements	8	6	24	17	13	10	62	46.3	27	20.1	24	22
Having sanitary system at school, helps girls to improve their learning	2	1.5	6	4.4	15	11.1	77	57.4	34	25.3	14	15
Stereotyping against girls improves their class enrolment and participation	8	6	22	16.4	0	0	41	30.5	63	47	22	21
Sensitization programs on girls education improve girls' success	21	15.7	7	5.2	16	12	49	36.5	41	30.5	18	24

Source: Primary source (2022).

The respondents were asked whether participation of girls in sports activities improve academic performance, and 20.8% responded strongly agree, 42.5% responded agree, 3% responded strongly disagree, 12% responded disagree. When asked whether participation of girls in leadership increases academic achievements, 20.1% answered strongly agree, 46.3% answered agree, 6% answered strongly disagree while 17% answered disagree. The respondents were asked if having sanitary system at school, helped girls to improve their learning, 25.3% answered strongly agree, 57.4% answered agree, 1.5% answered strongly disagree, while 4.4 answered disagree. They were asked whether stereotyping against girls improved their class enrolment and participation, 47% answered strongly agree, 30.5% answered agree, 6% answered strongly disagree, while 16.4% answered disagree. They were asked whether sensitization programs on girls education improve girls' success, 30.5% answered strongly agree, 36.5% answered agree, 15.7% answered strongly disagree, while 5.2 answered disagree. Briefly, this means that the effects of girls' policy implementation on female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education were positive because the majority responded that females' performance has increased at a better level. So, the schools staff was encouraged to include females in different teaching and learning activities to help them develop competences in their lessons.

Initially there was a large gap in terms of academic achievements between girls and boys but this gap has kept on decreasing over time. In 2017, girls outperformed boys in national exams in Primary and O'Level secondary. For example, in 2017, the pass rate of girls was 55% while boys pass rate was 45% (REB, 2017).

Interview with the respondents on the effects of girls' policy implementation

Head teachers described the effects related to girls' policy implementation on female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education in their school where they stressed on the higher grades earned by females students during their studies. The respondents confirmed that girls get required skills and use them in their everyday life such as using ICT in schools and at homes, using telephones computer and internet during their studies, peer positive influence among their colleagues.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the findings

The researcher summarized the study findings and found out that the implementation of girls' education policies in Twelve Year Basic Education in Gasabo District was practiced at medium level because the results showed that there was still some gap to fill so that every female student at schools be integrated for academic performances. Thereafter, the researcher was interested in examining the level of female students' academic achievements in Twelve Years Basic Education and analyzed information from teachers and head teachers in the sampled 12YBE schools. The results showed that since the girls' policy started its implementation in Twelve Years Basic Education, the level of female students' academic achievement has increased at distinctive level where both girls and boys get equal opportunity to perform different academic activities and both succeed.

5.2 Conclusions

The researcher was interested in assessing the girls' education policy implementation and female students' academic achievement in twelve years basic education in Rwanda, and has concluded by answering research questions. The respondents were asked about the extent has the girls' education policy been implemented in Twelve Years Basic Education in Gasabo district, and they concluded that the implementation of girls' policy in schools was at a good level despite some challenges which need to be addressed by the concerned people. In this research, the researcher has concluded that the level of female students' academic achievement in Twelve Years Basic Education was distinctive because female and male students perform effectively and all of them get equal opportunity on the quality education and gender equality. It was concluded that there were positive effects of girls' policy implementation on female students' academic achievement such as the female students getting the higher grades in class during their studies, getting required skills and use them in their everyday life such as using ICT in schools and at homes, using telephones computer and internet during their studies.

5.3 Recommendations of the study

The general objective of this study was achieved and the respondents of the study were eager to show their opinions on girls' education policy implementation and female students' academic achievement in twelve years basic education where the researcher addresses the following recommendations:

It was found out that the girls' policy implementation in twelve years basic education was distinctively achieving it overall goals. However, the journey to total implementation for academic achievement is still long.

It was revealed that the participation in learning for the females students in twelve years basic education was high, though there was some part that need to fill in. That is why the Ministry of Education should enhance the school head teachers and teachers in the inclusion of the female students in the different activities as males such as inclusive plays, sports and entertainments.

The parents and children in the families should also be encouraged to implement the norms and regulations of the family promotion in line with child right promotion by providing and receiving all necessary requirements to both females and males students to encourage them follow their lessons with purpose.

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